

ON MANAGEMENT AND THE LEARNING PROCESS

Linguistics

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Mirhat Aliu

Department of English Language and Literature
University of Tetovo – Prilep, North Macedonia.

Abstract

The aim of this paper is to clarify how management could be effective in the learning process, or better to say what is going to be the main idea of creating one successful management of learning process. With other words, in this paper I will try shortly to define the correct definition of management, what would be some important characteristics of management in the learning process, and of course I will try clearly to mention what is going to be one important element of creating an effective management in the learning process, which will affect positively in students' goals.

Introduction

First of all, there is the need where I should mention the fact that the title called “Management of learning process” – refers to a process of setting goals, planning, controlling and leading the execution of any type of activity. Which means management of learning process is very necessary to run any institution or organization. Also for this topic, it is important to mention that the techniques of management in the learning process are used by teachers in order the classroom to be focused on cooperation to direction of the class, and to ensure that students are not disruptive to their peers.

Since the school is institution, we need to deal with the fact that school requires proper management of education, students, teaching-learning process, staff etc. In simple words, management stands for the process of managing all the resources in a systematic manner for achieving predetermined task.

We can also say that management of learning process – is a process that allows teachers to control the learning and direction of their classroom.

Management of learning process – Defenition and some important characteristics

Learning management – is the capacity to design pedagogic strategies that achieve learning outcomes for students. The learning management concept was developed by Richard Smith of Central Queensland University (Australia) and is derived from architectural design which is best rendered as design with intent. Learning management then means an emphasis on the design and implementation of pedagogical strategies that achieve learning outcomes. In simple words, management stands for the process of managing all the resources in a systematic manner for achieving predetermined task.

A learning management system may also provide employees/students with the ability to use interactive features such as threaded discussions, video conferencing, and discussion forums to reach their full potential. It is important to mention that in management of learning process, it is the teacher who needs to control the learning and the direction of the classroom. Teachers use classroom management to keep students focused on learning while preventing disruption from slowing the learning process. A wide range of classroom management techniques are used by teachers and since classroom management keeps classes on track and prevent disruptions from slowing down the learning process, it's one of the most fundamental aspects of high quality education. Effective classroom management can often be the difference between a classroom that's focused and attentive and a classroom in which students struggle to achieve their educational objectives. Teachers face a variety of choices when it comes to classroom management. While some teachers take a direct approach to managing and directing their classrooms, others focus on building a friendly, collaborative relationship with their students. Classroom management can often be the difference between a focused classroom that achieves its educational goals and a classroom that falls behind the average in its category. As a teacher, having an understanding of classroom management and the ability to apply classroom management techniques gives you the power to keep your entire classroom focused on achieving its objectives and academically productive.

The Learning Process in Context

Kolb's model based on experiential learning theory identifies four modes in the learning cycle: Concrete Experimentation, Reflection, Abstract Conceptualization and Active Experimentation.

Basically, this is a fancy way of saying that we learn by: Doing something (Concrete Experimentation), Think about it (Reflection), Doing some research, Talking with others and applying what we already know to the situation (Abstract Conceptualization), Doing something

new or doing the same thing in a more sophisticated way based on our learning (Active Experimentation). These four learning cycle include our values and cultural influences, also comprises the values of the institution and the learning community created by the instructor.

Features of Management in the Learning process

Some important features of management in the learning process could be:

Motivation - through involvement of management, the teacher is made more conscious and encouraged towards his duties.

Better Relationship - with the help of proper management, a better relationship in the learning can be established.

Opportunities for Development - management provides opportunity to pupils for all round development.

The Challenges of Classroom Management

It's important to mention that teachers face a variety of classroom management challenges. These can include disruptive students that slow or interrupt the pace of learning and ineffective or poorly thought out management techniques that worsen student behavior. The most effective teachers typically understand a variety of effective classroom management techniques and use the most appropriate solution to keep their class free of disruption and focused on achieving its educational goals.

What we Should Know about Classroom Management

Classroom management can often be the difference between a focused classroom that achieves its educational goals and a classroom that falls behind the average in its category. As one teacher, having an understanding of classroom management and the ability to apply classroom management techniques, gives you the power to keep your entire classroom focused on achieving its objective and academically productive.

For management of learning process it is important also to mention and these characteristics: **Management Encourages Initiative** - Initiative means to do the right thing at the right time without being told or influenced. **Management Encourages innovation** - Innovation brings new ideas, new technology, new methods etc. This makes the learning process more effective and more powerful. **Facilities Growth and Expansion** - Management in learning process makes optimum utilization of resources.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is important to mention that management in the learning process –the proper planning builds confidence in the teacher and provides opportunity to both teacher and learner to make best use of abilities, labour and time. Management helps in proper organization control of physical facilities and overall classroom environment. It identifies the need of learner and organizes all necessary requirement of curricular content. So, with few words we can say that management set measures and outcomes which will enable an institution to assess rigorously how well the learning objectives are being achieved. Management encourages better teacher pupil relationship, close cooperation and healthy ntegration in the process of instruction.

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